

VALKYRIES

D3.3 Report on data protection and IP boundaries in the applicable framework

Reference Number: D3.3

Ed/Rev: A/0

Main Contributor: SSSA

Other Contributors: INDRA, TAS, NOVOTEC, BDI, HESE

Date: 18/07/2023

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101020676

Editors

Name	Contact	Entity
Denise Amram	Denise.amram@santannapisa.it	SSSA
Giovanni Comandé	Giovanni.comande@santannapisa.it	SSSA

Contributors

Name	Entity	Contribution
Camilla Signoretta	SSSA	Table of Content (ToC)
Irina Carnat	SSSA	First draft §4
Ignacio Hernández Palencia	NOVOTEC	Review
José Cabezas	NOVOTEC	Review
Miguel Gaspar	HESE	Review; formatting
Merixtell Bassols Tayeda	INDRA	Review
Carmen Martín Curto	TASSICA	Review
Manuel Ocaña	INDRA	Quality review

Document Changes Record

Edit./Rev.	Date	Chapters	Reason for change
A/0	18/07/2023	All	Original document

Content

1. Executive Summary	1
2. Identification	2
3. Document and Project Scope	3
3.1 Project Overview	3
3.2 Document Structure.....	3
4. Requirements compliance matrix	4
5. EU legal framework applicable to data management.....	5
5.1. Personal and non-personal data protection and governance	5
5.2. The role of the GDPR.....	5
5.3. The role of Free Flow Regulation	7
5.4. The role of the Open Data Directive	7
5.5. The role of the Data Governance Act.....	9
5.6. The role of the Data Act Proposal	11
5.7. The role of the proposal of Regulation on Interoperable Europe Act	14
5.7.1. Lesson learnt from VALKYRIES: conditions to boost the legal interoperability ..	16
6. Barriers to the data strategy implementation in first response scenarios	19
6.1. Lack of data	19
6.2. National safeguards and cross-border scenarios.....	19
6.3. Budgetary constraints, towards budgetary interoperability.....	20
7. Data management for first response activities: policies and recommendations	22
7.1. Clauses and legal standards to collect, store, share, and reuse data in crisis management technologies.....	22
7.1.1. Collection of data	22
7.1.2. Access to data.....	23
7.1.3. Secondary use of data	24
7.2. Proposal of Terms and Conditions for the VALKYRIES ecosystem implementation ...	27
8. Conclusions.....	30
9. Annex A – References and bibliography	31
10. Annex B – Glossary	33

Tables

Table 1 - Requirements compliance matrix.....	4
Table 2 - Impact of Data Act on relevant issues	13
Table 3 - VALKYRIES approach facing the Interoperable Europe Act challenges	16
Table 4 - Data portability gaps and enablers.....	17
Table 5 - Data subjects’ oversight and data control gaps and enablers	18
Table 6 - Cross-border legal impact from VALKYRIES Use-Cases.....	20
Table 7 - Recommendations on budgetary interoperability	21
Table 8 - Clauses for data collection.....	23
Table 9 - Clauses for data access	24
Table 10 - Clauses for secondary uses of data in emergency scenarios	25
Table 11 - Clauses for secondary uses of data after the emergency.....	27
Table 12 - Proposal of Terms and Conditions.....	29
Table 13 - Glossary	33

1. Executive Summary

This deliverable provides an overview of the new legislative initiatives that may impact on the VALKYRIES ecosystem under the data protection safeguards and intellectual property rights perspectives. It refers to the current updates on data strategy and it includes policy and recommendations for establishing a tailored and effective governance of the data flows in the emergency situations, aiming to facilitate the adoption of the VALKYRIES ecosystem by first responders' organizations.

2. Identification

Deliverable Title: Report on data protection and IP boundaries in the applicable framework

Deliverable Id: D3.3

Deliverable Title Abbreviation: D3.3

Name of lead participant: SSSA

Name of Contributors: INDRA, TAS, NOVOTEC, BDI, HESE

Type: Report

Dissemination Level: Public (PU)

Proposed Classification Level: Non-Restricted

Reporting Conditions: Funding Requirement (FR)

Linked project Work Package: WP3 – Responsible innovation, certification, exploitation

Linked project tasks: T3.3 – Identification of relevant ethical, legal and societal aspects between hard law and soft law

Action: Design

Status: First Release

Document Layout: VALKYRIES official template

Details: This specification applies to the project VALKYRIES: Harmonization and Pre-Standardization of Equipment, Training and Tactical Coordinated procedures for First Aid Vehicles deployment on European multi-victim Disasters funded under the SU-DRS03-2018-2019-2020 (IA), subtopic 3 Grant Agreement of the Horizon 2020 (H2020) tendering conditions. The document identifies the relevant ethical, legal and societal aspects between hard law and soft law.

3. Document and Project Scope

This document builds up an updated state of the art of the current European Union (EU) data strategy in order to identify mechanisms to properly develop procedure of data governance (collection, access, and sharing) in compliance with the data protection safeguards and intellectual property rights, emerging from hard law and soft law frameworks applicable to the VALKYRIES ecosystem.

3.1 Project Overview

VALKYRIES aims to develop pre-standardised and harmonised procedures for first responders. In this frame, data collection, access, and sharing procedure are crucial to develop efficient crisis management models that could be applied in different scenarios and in cross-borders contexts. The legal analysis developed in this deliverable will explore the possible legal conditions to strengthen the interoperability of the VALKYRIES model.

3.2 Document Structure

This document includes a general overview of the relevant framework; the description of the issues emerged in the project; the analysis of needs of harmonisation to improve standards on these profiles.

4. Requirements compliance matrix

Description of the requirements can be consulted in D2.7 – Definition of System Requirements and Demonstration Use Cases document.

ID	Priority	Traceability	WBS Deliverables	Compliance	Results
REQ_BASE_T 3.3_1	P1	VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-9	D3.3	REQUIRED	§7
REQ_COM_T 3.3_3 BUDGETARY	NA	VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-8	D3.3	RECOMMENDED	§5.3.3

Table 1 - Requirements compliance matrix

5. EU legal framework applicable to data management

5.1. Personal and non-personal data protection and governance

A 'single European data space' is referred to as a genuine single market, open to data sharing from across the world – where personal as well as non-personal data, including sensitive business data, are secure and businesses also have easy access to an almost infinite amount of high-quality industrial information, boosting growth and creating value, while minimizing the human carbon and environmental footprint¹.

Data spaces are designed to overcome legal and technical barriers to data sharing by combining the necessary tools and infrastructures and addressing issues of trust by way of common rules. A common European data space brings together relevant data infrastructures and governance frameworks in order to facilitate data pooling and sharing².

The novel approach of the EU Data strategy involves establishing a comprehensive set of rules that are applicable to all data spaces, regardless of the particular industry and despite the parallel approach to specifically regulate the expected European Data Spaces.

In the following paragraphs, we will analyze the different EU legislative initiatives that are shaping the VALKYRIES ecosystem, taking into account the opportunities of designing an effective personal and non-personal data governance strategy for disasters management.

We will refer both to enacted as well as applicable laws and to relevant only approved as well as published proposals, providing a tailored crossed-analysis of the interpretative tools aiming to boost the data management activities as developed in VALKYRIES.

To this end, policy and recommendations will be inspired to comply with fairness, non-discrimination, and transparency as well as to boost an effective interoperability in the organizations of first responders.

5.2. The role of the GDPR

The EU Reg. 2016/679 on General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) protects natural persons regarding the processing of personal data and ensures the free movement of such data. As known, it entered into application in May 2018 and it constitutes the main pillar of the data strategy as it develops the boundaries between information that shall be protected in light of the prevalence of individuals' privacy protection, and the free circulation under specific safeguards and technical measures.

As stated in other deliverables (e.g., in D3.1), the harmonization of the data protection legal framework within the EU, that inspired many other extra-EU legislations, turned into a new ethical approach for a number of sectors. The legislative technique – that is common to the other Data Strategy initiatives - consists of a series of recitals (namely 173) addressing the overall interpretation of the principles and obligations stated in the articles, including principles, rights of the data subjects, controllers and processors, transfers to third countries, independent supervisory authorities, cooperation and consistency, remedies, liability and penalties, provisions relating to specific processing situations, general and final provisions.

¹ European Commission, Communication "A European Strategy for Data", COM(2020) 66 final, sec. 3, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52020DC0066>.

² Commission Staff Working Document on Common European Data Spaces, SWD (2022) 45 final, p. 2

In short, under article 5 and ff GDPR to process personal data in a lawful, fair, and transparent manner, the data controller shall implement technical and organizational measures to meet the purpose limitation, data minimisation, accuracy, storage limitation, integrity and confidentiality requirements. In addition, the principle of accountability allocates the burden of the proof related to the compliance activities on data controllers. Such a risk-based approach combines hard law (obligations and enforcement tools, auditing, authorizations, report and monitoring, sanctions) and soft law instruments (opinions, standards, codes of conducts, self-regulation, binding corporate rules, ...) in order to properly address daily needs, priorities, and urgencies. This approach allows a strategic efforts and resources allocation in light of the overall conditions of those who are responsible to mitigate risks on fundamental rights protection for a given activity.

Very often data processing activities encompass both personal and non-personal data. GDPR applies only to personal ones although it acknowledges at referral 26 that their borderlines are fluid. Accordingly, pseudonymised data (i.e., that information that can disclose one's identity only if associated to other ones) are included in its scope of application.

Considering the broader category of personal data, their flows can be classified as general data-related or sensitive-data-related (in the GDPR language "special categories" of data). The former ones refer to personal information that may identify data subjects, while the second ones refer to that information that may expose the data subject to a direct or an indirect discrimination, including racial or ethnic origins, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, or trade union membership, as well as the processing of genetic data, health-related data or sex life or sexual orientation.

In line with art. 8 of the European Charter of Fundamental Rights, appropriate legal bases for data processing shall be identified respectively within article 6 GDPR for the general data (contractual relationship, legal obligation to be accomplished by the data controller, data subject's vital interest, public interest, legitimate interest of the data controller) and article 9 GDPR for the sensitive ones. The latter shall not be processed unless a specific legal basis has been identified.

Article 9, para 2, sub a)-j) identifies the following legal conditions: data subject's explicit consent, legal obligation to be accomplished by the data controller, data subject's vital interest, legitimate activities with appropriate safeguards by a foundation, association or any other not-for-profit body with a political, philosophical, religious or trade union aim, manifestly made public data, or to establish, exercise or defence within a legal claims, or for reasons of substantial public interest – within the purposes of preventive or occupational medicine – or for the assessment of the working capacity of the employee, or for medical diagnosis and health or social care, or to manage the related services, or the necessity for reasons of public interest in the area of public health, research and statistics purposes. Emergency scenarios are therefore lawfully enabling personal and sensitive data processing activities.

To this end, considering who is determining means and purposes of the data processing, flows of information can be governed by a single data controller, or by joint data controllers at the conditions agreed under article 26 GDPR, or on behalf of the data controller(s) by a data processor appointed under article 28 GDPR.

IMPLICATION These few pills of GDPR structure and obligations are useful to shape the boundaries of the applicable framework for a data management strategy aiming to centralize

triage operations into a platform (SIGRUN) able to enable different data flows according to the different procedure of response and the victims' needs.

To this end as a complementary ground of analysis, the free circulation of non-personal data constitutes a pillar of the entire system.

5.3. The role of Free Flow Regulation

Free flow of non-personal data Regulation³ mainly addresses data localization data, laying down rules on the processing of such data, their availability and portability for professional users (Article 1). It only applies to non-personal data -i.e. all data other than the personal ones as defined in article 4 GDPR - without prejudice to the relevant personal data protection legislation covering the same matter.

The Regulation has effectively removed data localization requirements imposed by Member States, which were identified as significant barriers to (cross-border) data sharing, unless they are justified for reasons of public security and in accordance with the principle of proportionality⁴, as stated in Article 4 of the Free Flow Regulation.

In order to facilitate the free circulation of flows, article 6 of the Regulation introduces a self-regulatory approach to promote seamless data portability among professional users of cloud service providers.

This provision mandates the Commission to actively support and streamline the development of codes of conduct for service providers, specifically in the cloud sector⁵. These codes of conduct are expected to include best practices, minimum information requirements, and certification schemes.

IMPLICATION Considering the VALKYRIES approach, the limits to the free-flow of non-personal data collected and managed by SIGRUN shall be imposed by specific "public security" reasons, included therefore in ad hoc provisions and justified in terms of proportionality.

5.4. The role of the Open Data Directive

The Open Data Directive⁶, enacted in 2019, repealing the Public Sector Information (PSI) Directive⁷, aims at facilitating and regulating access to data held by the public sector and specific public undertakings (government to business (G2B)), as well as publicly funded research data, enabling its commercial or non-commercial use without charge, by setting up minimum harmonized rules and practical arrangements (Article 9). However, it is important to notice that the Directive solely apply to data which are already accessible based on existing European and national access regimes: as such, the Open Data Directive does not establish new rights⁸. Moreover, it only concerns non-personal data, data which are not subject to IP rights of third

³ Regulation (EU) 2018/1807 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 November 2018 on a framework for the free flow of non-personal data in the European Union.

⁴ Commission Staff Working Document, On the free flow of data and emerging issues of the European data economy, accompanying the document Communication Building a European data economy, SWD(2017) 2 final, 2017, p. 5.

⁵ Leistner M., Antoine L. (2022), *op. Cit.*, p. 38.

⁶ Directive (EU) 2019/1024 on open data and the re-use of public sector information, OJ L 172/56 ('Open Data Directive').

⁷ Directive 2003/98/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 November 2003 on the re-use of public sector information.

⁸ Leistner M., Antoine L. (2022), *op. Cit.*, p. 39.

parties, and data or documents which are not qualified as confidential information (Article 1), therefore the research data made as open as possible and as close as necessary within the VALKYRIES ecosystem are included in the field of application of this legislation.

With reference to *sui generis* rights on databases, Article 1(6) specifies that this right ‘*shall not be exercised by public sector bodies in order to prevent the reuse of documents or to restrict reuse beyond the limits set by this Directive*’. Precisely in these limitations in the scope of applicability, it is complemented by the Data Governance Act, not without possible overlaps. Article 4 establishes the procedure for the processing of requests for re-use, while Article 5 specifies the available formats for re-use.

In summary, the documents must be available in “*in formats that are open, machine-readable, accessible, findable and re-usable, together with their metadata. Both the format and the metadata shall, where possible, comply with formal open standards*”, in accordance with the principle of ‘open by design and by default’, which should not entail disproportionate effort.

In general, the Directive lays down rules for non-discrimination and fair trading of data, which shall ensure that the applicable conditions for secondary uses shall not be discriminatory for comparable categories of re-use (Article 11), whereas exclusive contractual arrangements, subject to regular review, may be put into place for the provision of a service in the public interest (Article 12).

On the other hand, the Open Data Directive does cover ‘dynamic’ data and establishes specific conditions for the so-called high-value datasets (Articles 13 ff), such as geospatial or meteorological data, data relating to earth observation and environment, statistics, companies and company ownership and mobility (Annex I). The identification of specific high-value datasets is determined by evaluating their potential to generate significant socioeconomic or environmental benefits, innovative services, widespread user benefits (particularly for Small Medium Enterprises (SMEs)), revenue generation, and compatibility with other datasets.

From this perspective, datasets that could be generated by the SIGRUN application can address one or more of the six high value ones identified by the directive. Therefore, once the emergency circumstances have been managed information pooled by personal and confidential data must be exploited for further uses.

***IMPLICATION* Conditions could be set in order to ensure fairness and inclusiveness both in the access for secondary use and for allowing further processing.**

To this end, a general code of conduct including general principles and specific provisions could be developed in order to allow a harmonized approach towards data sharing. For example, common fees could be set in order to get access to cross-border data for the same purposes; a common procedure of request could be agreed in order to identify non-discriminatory conditions to allow access and reuse of the collected information, such as in terms of time for processing the request, reports and outcomes to be communicated to the platform after the secondary uses and processing activities, possible limitations for sharing in third party countries and or to targeted organizations in light of specific public safety needs, conditions for allowing data altruism under the following illustrated Data Governance Act.

5.5. The role of the Data Governance Act

The **Data Governance Act**⁹ (DGA) aims to facilitate the sharing and re-use of certain categories of data held by public sector bodies (PSBs) that is subject to the rights of others. More specifically, according to Article 3, the grounds for protection of such data are: (a) commercial confidentiality; (b) statistical confidentiality; (c) protection of intellectual property rights of third parties; (d) protection of personal data. *It complements the EU Directive on open data and the re-use of public sector information but focuses on data held by public sector bodies that fall outside the scope of the Open Data Directive.* The Open Data Directive requires PSBs to share their held documents in an open data format, which allows free and unrestricted use, reuse, and sharing by anyone. In contrast, the aim of the EC with the DGA is to strike a balance by enabling the reuse of data that is subject to third-party rights through more specific schemes than the open data approach of the Open Data Directive.

As such, the Regulation does not grant -thus it does not create an obligation- the right to re-use such data but establishes harmonized conditions for its potential re-use, including the requirement of non-exclusivity, in accordance with Article 4. **As such, the DGA does not establish access or use rights for such data**¹⁰.

The Regulation draws inspiration from the principles of data management and re-use that have been developed for research data. These principles, known as the FAIR data principles, emphasize that data should ideally be findable, accessible, interoperable, and re-usable. By incorporating these principles, the DGA aims to ensure that the shared data among businesses is organized and structured in a way that makes it easier to discover, access, exchange, and process in order to conduct innovative data analysis and shape new solutions, services, and products. The FAIR (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability) principles promote openness, transparency, and collaboration, allowing data to be effectively utilized for various purposes across different sectors. By aligning with these principles, the Regulation seeks to establish a framework that encourages data sharing and re-use in a manner that benefits businesses and promotes innovation while also safeguarding data protection, privacy, and confidentiality.

The Regulation aims to address barriers to a well-functioning data-driven economy and establish EU values-centred governance framework for data access and use (Recital 4). The underutilization of certain categories of data held by PSB (Recital 5), such as commercially confidential data, data subject to statistical confidentiality, and data protected by intellectual property rights of third parties, is a significant challenge to deal with. This is due to the sensitivity of this data, which requires meeting specific technical and organizational procedural requirements before it can be made available. As a result, these data categories often remain inaccessible even for research or innovative activities.

To enable the safe re-use of personal and commercially confidential data (Recital 6), privacy-friendly analyses techniques, such as anonymization, pseudonymization, differential privacy, generalization, suppression, and randomization, can be applied. Together with comprehensive

⁹ Regulation (EU) 2022/868 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 May 2022 on European data governance and amending Regulation (EU) 2018/1724 (Data Governance Act).

¹⁰ Leistner M., Antoine L. (2022), IPR and the use of open data and data sharing initiatives by public and private actors, p. 41.

data protection approaches, these techniques ensure the protection of data privacy and enable the re-use of such data for research, innovation, and statistical purposes.

This Regulation (Recital 7) emphasizes that the categories of data held by public sector bodies subject to re-use fall outside the scope of the Open Data Directive, which excludes data that is not accessible due to commercial and statistical confidentiality and data for which third parties hold intellectual property rights. Competition law compliance is essential for public sector bodies (Recital 9) when establishing re-use principles. Agreements that create exclusive rights for certain data re-use should be avoided unless they are justified and necessary for providing a service of general interest. Public procurement rules should be followed, and regular reviews based on market analysis should be conducted to assess the ongoing necessity of exclusivity.

IMPLICATION The DGA framework is therefore particularly relevant for developing terms and conditions of SIGRUN usability as under the VALKYRIES project a FAIR ecosystem has been already established and developed.

The opportunities to implement SIGRUN within first responders are dealing with the DGA mechanisms of access, intermediary activities, and reuse of data generated, collected and processed for a primary purpose, like in case of emergency.

In fact, according to the DGA, PSBs (state, regional or local authorities, bodies governed by public law or associations formed by one or more of these authorities or by one or more of such bodies governed by public law) are free to allow or deny the access, use and re-use of public data. In particular, they can charge the request in case of datasets protected by: a) commercial confidentiality; b) statistical confidentiality; c) protection of the intellectual property rights of third parties; d) protection of personal data.

If the request of data flows is a cross-border one, the following obligations are set:

- i) According to article 4, the prohibition of concluding agreements or other practices of exclusivity for the re-use of data, unless the exclusivity is necessary for the provision of a service or product of general interest which would not otherwise be possible. The exclusivity period of the right to reuse data must not exceed three years;
- ii) According to article 5, conditions of re-use public shall be "non-discriminatory, proportionate and objectively justified in relation to the categories of data, the purposes of the re-use and the nature of the data for which reuse is permitted". Conditions could be imposed to preserve the integrity of the functioning of the technical systems of the secure processing environment used and to guarantee the commercial confidentiality of the data to protect intellectual property rights. As a consequence, the PBs shall be able to verify the results of the data processing carried out by the re-user and reserve the right to prohibit any further ones if they could compromise the rights and interests of third parties;
- iii) As already highlighted, according to the systematic interpretation with the other initiatives on data strategy, especially the GDPR, third parties can be obliged to reuse only previously anonymised/pseudonymised data as well as to access and reuse the data only within a secure processing environment, even physical, provided and controlled by the public sector, complying with the implementation of technical solutions.

IMPLICATION Therefore, according to the Data Governance Act, the data protection and intellectual property rights boundaries shall prevail on data sharing and reuse by implementing technical and organizational safeguards that could protect data flows before the access and also

after the reuse in case from the further data processing possible third parties interests (both data protection-related and intellectual property ones) could be violated by the resulting analysis, solution, service, or product.

In this framework, a significant principle has been established to foster data reuse: the so-called data altruism, introduced by article 16 ff as a MS obligation to promote such a mechanism by establishing policies to “assist data subjects in making personal data related to them held by public sector bodies available voluntarily for data altruism, and set out the necessary information that is required to be provided to data subjects concerning the re-use of their data in the general interest”. Organizations of data altruism shall be identified and recognized in a public EU register, operating on a not-for-profit basis and be legally independent from any entity that operates on a for-profit basis. They also need to fulfill reporting duties and transparency requirements, by a series of organizational measures aiming to keep records of those who are exercising rights of data altruism, the information related to duration of personal and non-personal data flows, purposes of the data processing, any possible fees if applied.

Article 21 refers to the specific requirements to safeguard rights and interests of data subjects and data holders with regard to their data, including information ones on the terms and conditions for third parties to get access to their data; possible location of and the objectives of general interest for which it permits any processing carried out in a third country.

Moreover, misleading marketing practices to solicit the provision of data are prohibited.

Consent of data subjects and permission of data holders’ collection, storage and management is a paramount ground of data altruism organizations obligations: they shall provide tools for obtaining consent as well as for easy withdrawal of such consent or permission.

The infrastructure shall be safe and any breach, consisting of any unauthorized transfer, access or use of the data, shall be managed and reported to data holders and subjects without delay.

A rulebook will be adopted to define common and appropriate details as well as monitoring mechanisms for such compliance activities will be supervised by the competent authorities.

5.6. The role of the Data Act Proposal

The **Data Act proposal**¹¹ aims to open up specific markets related to the Internet of Things (IoT) and cloud sector. It includes provisions for contractual data sharing, reducing technical obstacles, and enabling data access in exceptional circumstances. The Data Act proposes decentralized structures for data access, use, sharing, and portability, which goes beyond the current centralized framework. The proposal has the goal to ensure fairness in the allocation of value from data among actors in the data economy and to foster access to and use of data. It also aims to empower individuals with respect to their data, and better equip businesses and public sector bodies with a proportionate and predictable mechanism to tackle major policy and societal challenges, including public emergencies and other exceptional situations.

The regulation specifically aims to increase access to and use of data while preserving incentives for value generation, providing legal certainty and fairness in data sharing contracts.

¹¹ Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on harmonised rules on fair access to and use of data (Data Act), COM(2022) 68 final.

As a consequence, it will enable public sector use of enterprise data in exceptional situations to support evidence-based policies and services, like the case of VALKYRIES field of application.

IMPLICATION By establishing safeguards against unlawful data transfer by cloud service providers, it will contribute to enhancing trust in the European data economy and in particular, in the technical solutions applied to the emergency scenarios, like the centralized system of data management developed within the SIGRUN platform.

In this context, interoperability standards for data sharing across different sectors and common European data spaces will be developed, also supporting the establishment of standards for smart contracts to ensure data sharing conditions are respected. In this regard, possible evolutions of our suggestions proposed as terms and conditions to use SIGRUN and reuse the generated flows of data, could constitute a very first example of virtuous mechanism enabled by the EU data strategy.

Furthermore, the consistency of the Data Act with the other data strategy initiatives shall be ensured. To this end the following enablers have been identified in the explanatory memorandum¹².

Issue	Consistency enablers included in the Data Act
Personal data protection	The proposal aligns with existing rules to protect personal data and confidentiality, while clarifying rights and obligations regarding data sharing.
Free Flow of Non-Personal Data Regulation and vendor lock-in	The proposal builds upon existing regulations to promote the free movement of non-personal data, address vendor lock-in issues, and facilitate switching between cloud service providers.
International data processing, storage, and transfers requirements.	The proposal adheres to GDPR regulations and trade commitments, ensuring lawful and secure cross-border data transfers.
Competition law and anti-trust regulations	The proposal considers competition law principles, including merger control and preventing abusive market dominance related to data sharing.
Database Directive and protection of databases	The proposal addresses legal uncertainties by clarifying the protection of databases containing data generated or obtained through product use or related services
Platform to Business Regulation and transparency obligations	The proposal aligns with transparency requirements for platforms, ensuring business users are informed about the data generated by the services provided
Open Data Directive and re-use of public sector data	The proposal complements rules on reusing public sector data and encourages interoperability of public services.
Interoperability for cross-border public services	The proposal supports the Interoperable Europe initiative, promoting cooperation and interoperability of digital solutions in the public sector
Data altruism	The proposal complements the Data Governance Act by facilitating voluntary data sharing among individuals and businesses while harmonizing conditions for public sector data use.

¹² Data Act, Explanatory Memorandum, p. 4 ff.

Issue	Consistency enablers included in the Data Act
Data portability	The proposal aligns with the Digital Markets Act, which aims to enhance portability of data generated through business and end-users' activities by gatekeeper platforms.
Intellectual property rights and trade secrets	The proposal does not impact existing rules in intellectual property, except for the application of the sui generis right of the Database Directive, and ensures protection of trade secrets.
Circular economy and sustainable product initiatives	The proposal establishes clear rules for data access necessary for the circularity and sustainability of certain products throughout their lifecycle, as part of the European Digital Product Passport
Contract law and prevention of power imbalances	The proposal adapts contract law and other rules to improve conditions for data reuse and prevent abuses of negotiating power in contracts.

Table 2 - Impact of Data Act on relevant issues

IMPLICATION Considering the VALKYRIES ecosystem, the Data Act will be particularly relevant to exploit the technical solutions developed in order to manage crises through the data management interoperable and cross-border platform during for first response activities.

In fact, Chapter III, titled "Obligations for data holders legally obliged to make data available" outlines the overarching access principles when a data holder is legally required to provide data to a data recipient. This chapter does not directly enforce data access or sharing but instead establishes a framework regarding the obligations related to making data available. It encompasses all the regulations outlined in EU law or national implementations, which impose the duty on data holders to make data accessible. It's important to note that this chapter does not pertain to data access rights governed by the GDPR.

Chapter V deals with making data available to public sector bodies based on exceptional needs. Public sector bodies or Union institutions, agencies or bodies may use data held by an enterprise in exceptional cases, such as in response to public emergencies (Article 14). The lack of timely access to and use of the data requested must prevent the public sector body or Union institution, agency or body from effectively fulfilling a specific task in the public interest that has been explicitly provided in law. In other cases of exceptional need, the data holder making the data available should be entitled to compensation that includes costs related to making the relevant data available plus a reasonable margin (Article 15). Requests for data must be proportionate, clearly indicate the purpose to be achieved, and respect the interests of the enterprise making the data available (Article 17). Data made available to public sector bodies should only be used for the purpose for which they were requested, and the data should be destroyed once it is no longer necessary for the purpose stated in the request, unless agreed otherwise (Article 19). Such purpose limitation to "what is strictly necessary" applies also to the disclosure of trade secrets. Article 22 imposes obligations for mutual assistance and cross-border cooperation between public sector bodies and Union institutions, agencies, and bodies.

Furthermore, recitals 57 – 62 specify conditions and obligations for public sector bodies to make data available in the case of public emergency. This data sharing framework balances the public interest in accessing data for emergencies and exceptional needs while considering the legitimate interests of data holders and minimizing burdens on businesses, by promoting

transparency, proportionality, and protection of sensitive information in situations of public emergencies, such as public health crises, environmental disasters, natural disasters worsened by climate change, or major cybersecurity incidents. Additionally, exceptional needs may arise where data is necessary to prevent or aid in the recovery from a public emergency, data holders should be obligated to make data available to public sector bodies and Union institutions, agencies, or bodies upon request. To ensure legal certainty and minimize administrative burdens on businesses, data requests should be transparent and proportionate, with specific and clearly explained purposes. The once-only principle should be followed to avoid multiple requests for the same data. Requests justified by a public emergency should be made public promptly, and online availability of all such requests should be ensured. The obligation to provide data equips public sector bodies with the necessary knowledge to respond to emergencies and fulfill specific tasks mandated by law. Commercially sensitive information is protected, and the re-use of data under the Open Data Directive does not apply, except for official statistics produced using the obtained data. Personal data protection rules must be followed when including personal data in the data made available. For this reason, anonymization should be attempted, and if not possible, pseudonymization and aggregation techniques should be used. Data obtained based on exceptional need should only be used for the stated purpose unless agreed otherwise by the data holder. Once the data is no longer necessary, it should be destroyed unless alternative arrangements have been agreed upon. No compensation is expected in the case of public emergency, while for exceptional needs other than emergencies, reasonable compensation may be provided, not exceeding the costs incurred by the data holder. Data obtained can be shared for scientific research or analytical activities that public sector bodies cannot perform themselves, with compatibility and informing the data holder.

5.7. The role of the proposal of Regulation on Interoperable Europe Act

The Proposal of **Interoperable Europe Act**¹³ refers to the conditions enabling more efficient and secure exchange of data to provide seamless public services. In fact, according to the EU Commission, by regulating cross-border interoperability further developing and completing all the existing facets of the Digital Single Market will be possible.

To this end, the proposal aims to ensure a human-centric approach to interoperability implementation strategy under the EU values, as well as to shape a governance structure to facilitate public administrations and private organisations to develop shared interoperability solutions (e.g., frameworks, open specifications, open standards, applications, or guidelines).

In particular, it aims to *“develop a coherent, human-centric approach to cross-border interoperability of network and information systems which are used to provide or manage public services from policymaking to policy implementation, accompanied by a clear governance to streamline shared interoperability frameworks, solutions, guidelines and specifications in the context of provision of digital public services across EU borders”*¹⁴.

To this end the harmonisation of procedures is a pre-requirement to shape a coherent approach towards the enablement of the adoption of interoperable systems to supporting the principle of good administration and the free movement of personal and non-personal data within the Union by public services. This does not mean to develop only centralised systems of data management, but to encourage at all levels the necessity to develop common solutions and

¹³ Proposal for a Regulation of the EU Parliament and of the Council laying down measures for a high level of public sector interoperability across the Union, published on 18.11.2022.

¹⁴ *Ibidem*, p. 6.

applications as well as policies to strengthen cross-sector and cross-border interoperability, especially for network and information systems.

From this perspective, the VALKYRIES approach is completely aligned to these declared purposes as well as to the proposed risk-based approach, anticipating the compliance activities envisaged in the new regulatory initiative.

Interoperable Europe Act provision	VALKYRIES approach
<p>Art 1, §1 sub (a) interoperability assessment would be required where the intended set-up or modification affects one or more network and information systems used for the provision of cross-border services across several sectors or administrations.</p> <p>Art. 1, §2 the interoperability assessment shall be performed before taking decisions on the legal, organisational, semantic or technical requirements for the new or modified network and information system in a binding manner</p>	<p>SIGRUN has been developed taking into account all the mentioned grounds, including: legal, organisational, semantic and technical requirements and standards (see WP3 activities).</p>
<p>Art. 1, §4 The interoperability assessment shall contain at least: (a) a description of the intended operation and its impacts on the cross-border interoperability of one or several network and information systems concerned, including the estimated costs for the adaptation of the network and information systems concerned; (b) a description of the level of alignment of the network and information systems concerned with the European Interoperability Framework, and with the Interoperable Europe solutions, after the operation and where it has improved compared to the level of alignment before the operation; (c) a description of the Application Programming Interfaces that enable machine-to-machine interaction with the data considered relevant for cross-border exchange with other network and information systems.</p>	<p>(a) VALKYRIES ecosystem includes the cross-border use-cases to test the approach.</p> <p>(b) VALKYRIES ecosystem has been developed considering the existing standards and procedures, even if the European Interoperability Framework has not been implemented yet.</p> <p>(c) Technical specifications of SIGRUN are included in the VALKYRIES outcomes.</p> <p>➔ Once approved, the public services and organisations that will apply SIGRUN for first response crisis management activities will be facilitated as the required information for that assessment are part of the cycle of the research carried out.</p>
<p>Art. 2. The shared content shall include the technical documentation and, where applicable, the documented source code, unless exceptions are met.</p>	<p>VALKYRIES ecosystem might encounter one or more exceptions, <i>e.g.</i> Intellectual property rights (IPRs) protection and public security, depending on the applicative context.</p>
<p>Art. 11 Establishment of Regulatory sandboxes.</p>	<p>VALKYRIES ecosystem could be a perfect candidate to set up a regulatory sandbox as it could foster innovation and facilitate the development and roll-out of innovative digital interoperability solutions for public services; facilitate cross-border cooperation between national competent authorities and</p>

Interoperable Europe Act provision	VALKYRIES approach
	synergies in public service delivery; enhance authorities' understanding of the opportunities or barriers to cross-border interoperability of innovative interoperability solutions, including legal barriers; contribute to the development or update of Interoperable Europe solutions.
Art. 15 Training	Training activities are considered as a priority in the development of the VALKYRIES solutions as a part of the pre-standardisation and harmonisation process for first responders.

Table 3 - VALKYRIES approach facing the Interoperable Europe Act challenges

5.7.1. Lesson learnt from VALKYRIES: conditions to boost the legal interoperability

In order to establish an efficient data governance and boost the legal interoperability, the following enablers and constraints have been identified to shape the tailored EU data strategy framework applicable to the VALKYRIES context. In particular, it is within this context that the Data Act (DA) and the DGA can be observed in their full regulatory effectiveness and impact¹⁵, considering as well as the possible boundaries set by budgetary constraints of stakeholders involved in first response activities.

Principle	Enabler interpretations	Constrains
Data Portability	<p>Data portability is not only referred to the individual right under article 20 GDPR, allowing to obtain and reuse one's personal data for their own purposes across different services, enabling the opportunities to move, copy or transfer personal data easily from one IT environment to another in a safe and secure way, without affecting its usability.</p> <p>Relationship between data access, data portability, and possible applicable costs for the data controller.</p>	<p>Although article 20 GDPR sets up an explicit personal data portability right for the data subjects, it has broader implications for data availability. Firstly, exercising the right to data portability does not automatically result in the deletion of the data in question, unless the data subject chooses to do so. Instead, it enables the transfer of data to different service providers. Secondly, where technically feasible, individuals have the right to request a direct transfer of their data to another service provider. However, the main challenge in implementing Article 20 GDPR lies not in the right itself, but in establishing the necessary infrastructure. This includes developing interoperable data formats, export and import tools, accessible interfaces, and APIs. The GDPR only requires controllers to provide personal data in a "structured, commonly used, and machine-readable format," while leaving the task of creating effective mechanisms for data portability to the industry. The right established in Article 20 GDPR does not</p>

¹⁵ Ducuing C., Margoni T., Schirru L. (edited by), White Paper on Data Act Proposal, CiTIP Working Paper 2022, p. 16.

Principle	Enabler interpretations	Constrains
		<p>strictly fall under the category of an "access right." Instead, it focuses on informing the data subject about the processing of their personal data, including the categories of data processed and the purposes for which they are processed. It also allows the data subject to verify the lawfulness of the data processing.¹⁶</p> <p>Information shall be provided free of charge for the data subject as a general principle.</p>
<p>Comments on VALKYRIES ecosystem: organisational, semantic, and technical requirements and standards followed to develop SIGRUN platform enables the portability of collected and shared information.</p>		

Table 4 - Data portability gaps and enablers

Principle	Enabler interpretations	Constrains
<p>Data subjects' oversight and control on data</p>	<p>The right of access under Article 15 GDPR aims to give individuals control over their personal data by allowing them to verify its lawfulness. It provides transparency and easy access to information about data processing.</p>	<p>Interplay between data access in public services.</p> <p>The right of access is an individual's right, separate from other rights, and should not be denied based on suspicions about its purpose, such as legal defense. Data controllers should focus on fulfilling the request and determining if they hold relevant personal data.¹⁷</p> <p>It's important to note that the GDPR applies not only to business-to-consumer (B2C) relationships but also to any situation involving personal data, including business-to-business (B2B), business-to-government (B2G), and government-to-business (G2B) interactions. However, the Court of Justice of the European Union (CJEU) has clarified that the right of access under EU data protection law has a distinct objective from the right of access to public documents, with the former aiming to provide individuals control over their personal data while the latter seeks transparency in decision-making processes of public authorities, and the right of access to personal data applies regardless of the existence of other types of access rights with</p>

¹⁶ Leistner M., Antoine L. (2022), IPR and the use of open data and data sharing initiatives by public and private actors, p. 37.

¹⁷ EDPB Guidelines 01/2022 on data subject rights – Right to Access, versión 1.0, adopte don 18 January 2022.

Principle	Enabler interpretations	Constrains
		different aims, such as in examination procedures. ¹⁸
	Data altruism under article 2, and 16 ff DGA enables the voluntary sharing of data on the basis of the consent of data subjects to process personal data pertaining to them through no profit organizations that will play the role of intermediates.	Data provided directly by data subjects/holders need to be pooled and shared in interoperable formats. Some costs shall be considered to this end.
<p>Comments on VALKYRIES ecosystem: the tools developed for the ethical and legal compliance as well as the library of standards will be useful to allow intermediates to pool data and make them interoperable with SIGRUN. Furthermore, the traceability of the flows will always allow data subjects to exercise their rights.</p>		

Table 5 - Data subjects' oversight and data control gaps and enablers

¹⁸ CJEU, Joined cases C-141/12 and C-372/12, YS and Others, para. 47.

6. Barriers to the data strategy implementation in first response scenarios

During the project development, a series of barriers have been addressed in order to achieve a higher level of legal, technical, semantic, and organizational harmonization required to shape an interoperable environment.

In the following subparagraphs, we will list them and suggest possible countermeasures that could be implemented in order to overcome the identified barriers.

6.1. Lack of data

The lack of data available in digital format constitutes a limitation for the design, development, and deployment of interoperable solutions that shall be tested across different sectors and countries for several reasons. In fact, most of the times, communication is only vocal in analogic way.

Mechanisms of cooperation between MS and international organizations for first response activities shall be put in place in order to converge data flows into the developed solutions for the following purposes:

- i) To centralize and harmonize TRIAGE procedures;
- ii) To improve the technical interoperability of the platform;
- iii) To be able to exploit information for statistics and further disasters prevention.

In fact, the challenge launched by the EU data strategy is related to the development of infrastructures able to collect, process and store high value datasets that could be reused for boosting innovation, progress and economic growth.

To this end, the current lack of data available is due both to the fact that common spaces and infrastructures are still in development and the awareness processes aiming to improve trusting mechanisms in data sharing are still ongoing.

VALKYRIES activities are contributing to these missions with the research outcomes of WP3, 4,5,6, but also through the ethical, legal, and standardization workshops that are developing awareness.

6.2. National safeguards and cross-border scenarios

Beyond the fragmented EU framework, another barrier against harmonization is given by the possible national legislations that could include more restrictive safeguards for data processing, sharing, and reuse. This constitutes, as stated in D3.1, a barrier especially when third countries are involved.

From the VALKYRIES Use-Cases we could address the following experiences (further details will be specified under T1.5-related Deliverables to be submitted by M24).

Country involved in the Use-Case	VALKYRIES approach to non-EU countries compliance activities	VALKYRIES approach to national safeguards introduced by MS for compliance activities:
Use-Case 1 Spain and Portugal	N.A.	National safeguards checked by involved partners. Not relevant on the compliance

Country involved in the Use-Case	VALKYRIES approach to non-EU countries compliance activities	VALKYRIES approach to national safeguards introduced by MS for compliance activities:
		activities performed under WP 8 and T1.5.
Use-Case 2 Greece and Bulgaria	Bulgarian partner committed to the ethical legal framework developed for the Consortium	National safeguards checked by involved partners. Not relevant on the compliance activities performed under WP 8 and T1.5.
Use Case 3 Italy and Slovenia	N.A.	National safeguards checked by involved partners. Not relevant on the compliance activities performed under WP 8 and T1.5.
Use Case 4 Norway	Norway adopts GDPR as EEA member.	N.A.

Table 6 - Cross-border legal impact from VALKYRIES Use-Cases

Therefore, the EU approach to export its data strategy beyond the borders has completely confirmed in the VALKYRIES ecosystem, confirming that the developed methodologies have not been affected by the cross-border legislative barriers. However, the context is particularly well placed to avoid / mitigate the impact of national laws on the EU ones, as the funding institution detailed the applicable laws and jurisdictions in the Consortium and Grant Agreements signed by the partners.

However, in B2B and B2G relationships the cross-border scenarios need to be addressed through the interpretative principles that the EU data strategy may offer in each initiative.

6.3. Budgetary constraints, towards budgetary interoperability

The first response actions are enabled in case of emergencies with authorizations from the competent authorities that are defining budget items and costs allowed to perform services and tasks in given circumstances.

To this end, the adoption of cross-border innovative solutions shall be considered also in terms of costs to be allocated for a series of activities aiming to make the product as interoperable and effective as possible.

To this end, some ways to ensure that budget constraints will not block emergency response according to the VALKYRIES results may be listed as follows.

Firstly, new technologies are optimizing tasks as the same data collection can be processed and shared for several activities, reducing time and increasing the efficiency and accuracy of information detected in triage activities otherwise performed in each step of the first response activity. The interoperability model defined in SIGRUN (D2.8 Architecture Design Document) defines the minimum set of data required to be transmitted for the management of a multi-victim incident and further defines the transmission protocol that allows the model to be easily implemented with existing systems.

Secondly, to invest into interoperable digital solutions shall be considered a first investment that then need to be maintained in terms of safety measures, software updates, technical features

in order to be applied in more and more contexts and through every day more effective tools. However, the introduction of a new standardize approach aiming to detect, process, and share data in open access platforms that could be feasible for different disasters scenarios constitutes an advancement in better frame costs of an emergency intervention.

Thirdly, the cross-border application allows to also identify compensation and cost sharing allocation according to possible procedures, requirements and conditions of the involved legal systems.

On the other hand, the introduction of ecosystems like the one developed in VALKYRIES requires prior training activities and time and resources to adapt the internal procedures and mechanisms of each organization to the new ones. During the demonstrations (UC1, UC2 and UC3) command and control tools have been used to demonstrate the harmonisation opportunities resulting from the project and it has been shown that they can be easily adapted to the SIGRUN reference model by integrating the data into the platform.

From the VALKYRIES experience it is possible to consider that the developed documenting and aligning methods are also promoting a comprehensive emergency response that complies with the budget balance of the intervening actors.

Recommendations to boost budgetary interoperability:

- To promote the application of Open Access solutions, developed in the framework of Research Infrastructures that are committed to Open Science will reduce in general costs of triage activities in terms of time and resources, providing a more accurate and efficient result.
- To develop codes of conducts and consistency mechanisms between first responders in order to be able to internally share best practices to share costs for the adoption of interoperable digital and cross-border solutions considering the different roles (and also possible reuse) of data in the given circumstances.
- To develop tailored information policies to promote data altruism in emergency situations in order to be able to reuse and exploit data for further uses and improve the ancillary mechanisms and procedures.
- To train and develop awareness among citizens and first responders to trust the application of Open solutions like the VALKYRIES ecosystem.
- Promote improved interoperability in existing systems if possible (legal ones) and design new systems on the basis of architectures that allow easy sharing of data in a federated model.

Table 7 - Recommendations on budgetary interoperability

7. Data management for first response activities: policies and recommendations

In this paragraph, we address some recommendations to enable data management activities for first response scenarios.

In particular, we focus on the clauses that can be used in the agreements and official authorizations to collect, store, and share data during the crisis management operations as well as the ones suitable to secondary uses of the collected and generated data for different purposes. In addition, we will propose possible terms and conditions for the VALKYRIES ecosystem, to be integrated and discussed under the exploitation plan at M24.

7.1. Clauses and legal standards to collect, store, share, and reuse data in crisis management technologies.

The following scenarios are designed to develop proper contractual clauses and standards considering the legal requirements to allow specific data processing activities. To this end, we propose guidelines for stakeholders to develop clauses and legal standards to pursue at the same the different interests that have been identified in the course of the VALKYRIES project as paramount to provide an interoperable legal framework for stakeholders.

7.1.1. Collection of data

The first step to properly establish the governance of given data flows is to identify data subjects and holders and to build up a paradigm aiming to protect and empower their fundamental rights.

Data collection can be enabled during the emergency directly from data subjects (for personal data) and data holders (for non-personal data) under the public interests' legal bases or through intermediates that could either belong to first responder or being automatically collected by wearable and allied technologies.

Collection \ Conditions	Collection during the emergency from data subjects through TRIAGE apps	Collection from first responders in loco or through allied technologies	Data generated by the allied technologies set for other purposes
Data subjects' rights	Privacy policy available in the App.	Privacy policy clause: Your personal data will be collected for the purposes of managing this emergency, for further information and details please visit our website or ask the available operator.	Privacy Policy required for the specific device shall include the possible use for emergency management.
Data governance	Data controller: App owner will perform as a data controller. It could be the public authority responsible for the crisis management.	Your personal data will be processed by the competent authorities and organizations, through instructed and authorized staff. For further information	Data controller: device owner: it could be either the public authority responsible for the crisis management or private and public owners. In

Collection \ Conditions	Collection during the emergency from data subjects through TRIAGE apps	Collection from first responders in loco or through allied technologies	Data generated by the allied technologies set for other purposes
	Data processors: the App administrator if different from the data controller.	and details please visit our website or ask the available operator.	case the device belongs to individuals, the data controller will be the competent authority responsible for the crisis management.

Table 8 - Clauses for data collection

7.1.2. Access to data

Second step is to provide access to the flows of data to those who need it for undertaking further actions both to take in charge individuals (e.g. for hospitals dispatching) and for infrastructural management purposes (e.g. traffic deviations, etc.).

In this regard, the principles that shall be considered are: the policy shall allow as more effective, granular, and accurate as possible access, considering pre-defined requirements, especially for dealing with individual and sensitive data flows.

Access to collected/generated data	Public authorities	First responders	Clinicians
Personal data	The request shall include the general conditions governing the lawfulness of processing by the controller; the types of data which are subject to the processing; the data subjects concerned; the entities to, and the purposes for which, the personal data may be disclosed; the purpose limitation; storage periods; and processing operations and processing procedures, including measures to ensure lawful and fair processing such as those for other specific processing situations. The Union or the Member State law shall meet an objective of public interest and be	The request shall include the general conditions governing the lawfulness of processing by the controller; the types of data which are subject to the processing; the data subjects concerned; the entities to, and the purposes for which, the personal data may be disclosed; the purpose limitation; storage periods; and processing operations and processing procedures, including measures to ensure lawful and fair processing such as those for other	Consent of data subjects, unless she can't provide it for individual data. Otherwise, the request will be processed under the legal basis of the reasons of public interest in the area of public health authorized by the competent legislative committees (at national /local level). Access is granted to staff committed to professional secrecy.

Access to collected/generated data	Public authorities	First responders	Clinicians
	proportionate to the legitimate aim pursued.	specific processing situations. The Union or the Member State law shall meet an objective of public interest and be proportionate to the legitimate aim pursued. In addition, for private bodies, authorization from the competent authority	
Non-personal data	The request shall include the performance of official duties in accordance with Union or national law	The request shall include the performance of official duties delegated by public authorities in accordance with Union or national law	The request shall be justified for public health purposes.

Table 9 - Clauses for data access

7.1.3. Secondary use of data

Third step is to allow the sharing mechanisms and secondary use of the accessed data. To this end, it is relevant to distinguish the purposes and the timeline of the reuse. In particular, during the emergency the re-use could be linked to the disaster management and through a system of authorizations the secondary use could be compared to the access request by third parties that are part of the following steps related to the first response activities. Conditions for secondary uses could be applied considering in any case the emergency legal basis. In addition, for all necessary participants to the SIGRUN platform to a given emergency and for the necessary data predefined in SIGRUN, purposes can be sufficiently defined ex ante enabling to exploit consent as a legal basis.

Secondary use of data during the emergency	Conditions	Possible legal basis	Data Governance	Monitoring mechanism for ensuring a fair, reasonable, and non-discriminatory data management.
Public authorities	Activities linked to the disaster management, including safeguards to	to protect the vital interests of the data subject or of	Single information point under DGA will manage requests.	Access cannot be denied unless it is proportionate and justified under an

Secondary use of data during the emergency	Conditions	Possible legal basis	Data Governance	Monitoring mechanism for ensuring a fair, reasonable, and non-discriminatory data management.
	avoid unauthorized access.	another natural person; Public interest if established in a law	The reuse will be enabled considering the public authority acting as data controller.	EU specific provision.
First responders	Activities linked to the disaster management, including safeguards to avoid unauthorized access.	to protect the vital interests of the data subject or of another natural person; Public interest if established in a law	Single information point under the DGA will manage requests. First responders will act as data controller.	NA
Clinicians	Healthcare reuse of information collected by third responders.	Healthcare services provision. Vital interests of individuals.	Once they process data flows for a different purpose, they will become data controller.	Access shall not be denied unless the reuse is considered in contrast with the EU fundamental rights.
Others	Authorization to get access for ancillary activities connected to the disaster management.	Legal basis connected to disaster management or other public interests as enabled by law. Private actors might leverage legitimate interest along with other art. 9 GDPR legal basis	Through intermediation services and/or single information point. They will act as data controllers.	Access could be conditioned in time and means to considering the needs of the emergency. In addition, fees, pre-established in the Terms and Conditions (T&C) of the platform.

Table 10 - Clauses for secondary uses of data in emergency scenarios

After the emergency, the reuse of data could be applied for several purposes other than the ones related to the disaster management and public interests, including the development of services and products, research and statistics, marketing etc. In this context, it is possible that fees and conditions could be applied and monitoring mechanisms to verify their nature and characteristics set up. For the secondary use of these data in the hands of Public administration can leverage the options opened by the DGA (see supra).

In the table below, we refer also to the criteria to be applied to ensure fair, reasonable, and non-discriminatory data management. This means that the T&C of the platform shall explicitly include the conditions for reuse, and justify them in terms of closeness as necessary. This means that any introduced criteria shall be considered proportionate and reasonable respect to the scope. To this end, the following recommendations are envisaged:

- I) To adhere to a code of conduct, if existing;
- II) To provide a self-assessment of the T&C under a fair, reasonable, and non-discriminatory data management;
- III) To include reporting and monitoring activities to verify whether the application of the conditions is effective;
- IV) To provide an external assessment either through a code of conduct, or through an independent committee/board etc.

Secondary use of data after the emergency	Conditions	Possible legal basis	Data Governance	Monitoring mechanism for ensuring a fair, reasonable and non-discriminatory data management
Public authorities	Activities linked to public interests pursued by the given public authority	Legal basis connected to disaster management or other public interests as enabled by law.	Data controllership for the reuse of personal data. T&C including conditions related to: - data retention after reuse; - license of results.	Criteria shall be transparent, non-discriminatory, fair, and public. Requests could be examined by a board.
First responders	Possible conditions applicable for pseudonymized data. Possible fees to be applied for certain uses, purposes, categories of first responders.	Legal basis connected to disaster management or other public interests as enabled by law. Private actors might leverage legitimate interest along with other art. 9 GDPR legal basis	Data sharing agreement to establish duration, means and purposes of the reuse, ownership and license of the results.	Criteria shall be transparent, non-discriminatory, fair, and public. Requests could be examined by a board.

Secondary use of data after the emergency	Conditions	Possible legal basis	Data Governance	Monitoring mechanism for ensuring a fair, reasonable and non-discriminatory data management
Clinicians	Consent	Vital interest Public Health Statistic scientific Research Private actors might leverage legitimate interest along with other art. 9 GDPR legal basis	Data controllership	Criteria shall be transparent, non-discriminatory, fair, and public. Requests could be examined by a board.
Research & statistics bodies	Conditions (e.g. the approval of an ethical committee, consent ...), fees, and reporting obligations can be introduced.	Statistics and Scientific research as along as a legal basis under art. 6 GDPR is applicable as well	Data sharing agreement to establish duration, means and purposes of the reuse, ownership and license of the results	Criteria shall be transparent, non-discriminatory, fair, and public. Requests could be examined by a board.
Others	Access could be conditioned in time and means to considering the needs of the emergency. In addition, fees, pre-established in the T&C of the platform	Legitimate Interests (marketing, etc)	-Data sharing agreement to establish duration, means and purposes of the reuse, ownership and license of the results	T&C shall be public, transparent, also introducing a tool aiming to evaluate different grounds of access and reuse providing an increasing fee

Table 11 - Clauses for secondary uses of data after the emergency

7.2. Proposal of Terms and Conditions for the VALKYRIES ecosystem implementation

In this paragraph, considering the above-mentioned grounds of analysis and the experience of the Use-Cases developed during the project, we designed possible clauses to be included in Terms and Conditions for the VALKYRIES ecosystem.

They are developed in order to grant openness designed explicitly for crisis management technologies, and directly resulting from the combination of traditional IP schemes and data protection principles.

Specific attention will be paid to monitoring mechanisms in order to ensure their fairness, reasonable, and non-discriminatory character.

Platform Management	Comments
<p>The platform management shall be set as the first step of its exploitation.</p> <p>In particular two models could be followed:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> i) The owner of the platform will also act as administrator of the platform, providing intermediation services for ingoing and outgoing data flows. ii) The owner of the platform identifies one or more services providers for the administration of the platform, acting as intermediary ones. 	<p>This issue has a priority relevance in order to develop the T&C of the platform.</p> <p>Ownership shall be referred to the infrastructure and to the datasets.</p> <p>Access for administration purposes shall be defined.</p> <p>Access for pooling activities shall be addressed.</p> <p>Different licenses can be applied for further reuse.</p>
Access to the platform	Comments
<p>The access to SIGRUN platform can be asked for free during a given emergency scenario, by private and public authorities that are committed to manage a given situation.</p>	<p>It shall be identified the administrator of the platform and its role (owner/supplier and corresponding obligations and rights)</p>
<p>The lists of authorised organisations are communicated by the local authorities managing the crisis, by identifying different level of access:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Public authorities b. First responders' organisations c. Hospitals and clinicians d. Other organizations 	<p>The list of the authorised organisations shall be adapted to the specific emergency, to the public/private nature of the user, considering the legal basis of the data processing. The platform should enable a flexible and swift adaptation of the relevant policies and notices (e.g. to data subjects).</p>
<p>Personal and non-personal data are collected, processed, and stored for all the duration of the emergency.</p>	<p>It shall be adapted considering the positions on the other sections.</p>
<p>The organisations shall be authorised with different levels of access according to the internal allocation of roles and responsibilities.</p>	<p>An annex could identify different levels of possible access.</p> <p>Conditions shall be clearly set for each level in order also to be assessed under the fairness, non-discriminatory, and reasonable grounds.</p>
<p>Staff with access shall be committed to specific confidentiality obligations</p>	<p>A tool of verification shall be implemented in the request interface for accountability purposes.</p>
Governance of data generated during the emergency	
<p>Data generated during the emergency will be stored in the platform as long as their availability, confidentiality, and integrity is preserved.</p>	<p>According to the exploitation plan it will be possible to tailor this</p>

<p>Once the emergency situation expired, data generated will be made as open as possible for further uses.</p> <p>After the conclusion of first response activities, appropriate technical and organisational measures shall be implemented to each dataset in order to timely make information sufficiently anonymous and set the conditions for reuse.</p> <p>Pseudonymised datasets could be made available only if:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - a lawful basis allows it - specific safeguards are introduced to protect fundamental rights of data subjects 	<p>part into different levels of data access and processing.</p>
Data curation after the emergency	
<p>After the emergency, data are stored with different levels of security according to their nature.</p> <p>Anonymous and aggregate datasets will be made freely findable, accessible and reusable in interoperable formats.</p> <p>Anonymised datasets and pseudonymised datasets will be findable through their metadata and accessible in an interoperable format upon request and appropriate legal basis.</p>	<p>This part could be tailored according to the definition of the exploitation plan and an annex could be added to define the items of the request and the criterion of evaluation in order to enhance transparency and avoid discriminatory behaviors.</p>
Secondary use of data generated during the emergency management	Comments
<p>Secondary use of data is always possible for anonymous and aggregate information.</p>	<p>N/A</p>
<p>Requests for processing anonymised and pseudonymised datasets shall include information about means and purposes, duration, and territoriality of data processing.</p> <p>Possible technical and organisational safeguards including data sharing agreements could be required for certain datasets.</p>	<p>An annex including different conditions according to the combination of the means, purposes, duration, and territoriality of the data processing could be added</p>

Table 12 - Proposal of Terms and Conditions

8. Conclusions

This report developed a cross-analysis among the EU initiatives on data strategy in order to shape the boundaries in terms of data protection and intellectual property laws emerging in the applicable framework.

The reconstruction of the applicable framework included both legislative initiatives already into force and newly approved ones that could impact in the near future on the matter.

To this end, considering the VALKYRIES ecosystem specific policy and recommendations to develop Terms and Conditions of platforms aiming to collect, process, and store data during and after an emergency have been addressed in order to allow an easier implementation from a legal view point of first response technologies among relevant organisations.

9. Annex A – References and bibliography

Alhadeff J., Van Alsenoy B., Dumortier J., The Accountability Principle in Data Protection Regulation: Origin, Development and Future Directions, In: Guagnin, D., Hempel, L., Ilten, C., Kroener, I., Neyland, D., Postigo, H. (eds) *Managing Privacy through Accountability*. Palgrave Macmillan, London, 2011, p. 49-82, DOI: https://doi.org/10.1057/9781137032225_4

Amram D., Denise Amram. Comparing EU Initiatives on Data: Addressing Risks and Enhancing Harmonisation Opportunities, *Opinio Juris in Comparatione*, 2023, 1-24.

Becker, R., Chokoshvili, D., Comandé, G., Dove, E. S., Hall, A., Mitchell, C., Molnár-Gábor, F., Nicolàs, P., Tervo, S., & Thorogood, A. (2022). Secondary use of personal health data: When Is It "further processing" under the GDPR, and what are the implications for data controllers? *European Journal of Health Law*, 1-29. <https://doi.org/10.1163/15718093-bja10094>

Colangelo G., Borgogno O. (2019) Data sharing interoperability: fostering innovation and competition through APIs. *CLSR* 35:105314

Davis FD. A technology acceptance model for empirically testing new end-user information systems: theory and results [doctoral dissertation]. Cambridge (MA): MIT Sloan School of Management; 1986.

P. Holub, F. Kohlmayer, F. Prasser, M.T. Mayrhofer, I. Schlünder, G.M. Martin, S. Casati, L. Koumakis, A. Wutte, L. Kozera, D. Strapagiel, G. Anton, G. Zanetti, O.U. Sezerman, M. Mendy, D. Valík, M. Lavitrano, G. Dagher, K. Zatloukal, G.J.B. van Ommen and J.E. Litton, 'Enhancing Reuse of Data and Biological Material in Medical Research: From FAIR to FAIR-Health', *Biopreservation and Biobanking* 16(2) (2018) 97–105. DOI: 10.1089/bio.2017.0110

Mantelero A (2018) AI and big data: a blueprint for human rights, social and ethical impact assessment. *CLSR* 34(4):754:772

Quinn P. (2016) The anonymisation of research data – a pyric victory for privacy that should not be pushed too hard by the EU data protection framework? *Eur. J. Health Law*. 24:1-21.

Leese M, Lidén K, Nikolova B. Putting critique to work: Ethics in EU security research. *Security Dialogue*. 2019;50(1):59-76. doi: 10.1177/0967010618809554

Vasileva, V., Application of a Human-Centric Approach in Security by Design for IoT Architecture Development. In: Gelenbe, E., Jankovic, M., Kehagias, D., Marton, A., Vilmos, A. (eds) *Security in Computer and Information Sciences*. EuroCybersec 2021. Communications in Computer and Information Science, vol 1596. Springer, Cham, 2022, pp.13-22, DOI: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-09357-9_2

Graef and M. Husovec 'Seven Things to Improve in the Data Act', *SSRN Electronic Journal*, 2022

J. Drexel et al. Position Statement of the Max Planck Institute for Innovation and Competition of 25 May 2022 on the Commission's Proposal of 23 February 2022 for a Regulation on harmonised rules on fair access to and use of data (Data Act)

E. Derclaye e M. Husovec, 'Why the sui generis database clause in the Data Act is counterproductive and how to improve it?' *SSRN Electronic Journal* 2022.

I Graef, R Gellert ' The European Commission's proposed Data Governance Act: some initial reflections on the increasingly complex EU regulatory puzzle stimulating data sharing' TLEC Discussion Paper , SSRN, 2021 https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3814721

10. Annex B – Glossary

Acronym	Description
B2B	Business to Business
B2C	Business to Consumer
B2G	Business to Government
CJEU	Court of Justice of the European Union
DA	Data Act
DGA	Data Governance Act
ELSA	Ethical, Legal and Societal Aspects
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
G2B	Government to Business
IoT	Internet of Things
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
NA	Not Applicable
PSBs	Public Services Bodies
PSI	Public Sector Information
R&D&I	Research & Development & Innovation
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
SME	Small Medium Enterprise
SOP	Standard Operating Procedure
ToC	Table of Content
T&C	Terms and Conditions

Table 13 - Glossary